

Review

Managing marine resources sustainably – But how do we know when marine management has been successful?

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ABSTRACT

Current marine environmental management is the ‘sustainable management of people and their marine activities’ to be achieved through ecosystem manipulation and activity control. Marine management *per se* needs to define who requires and can achieve a successfully managed environment, the tools and indicators for that management, the indications of success and the means of knowing that the environment has been successfully managed. Indicators of success require policies and plans, environmental targets and regulatory standards and guidelines, i.e. output controls such as those stipulated by legislation. It should aim for sustainable outcomes based on government policy, to satisfy public demands and using the advice and assessments by natural and social scientists. The inputs, outputs and outcomes should include scientific research and advice, reporting to the government and the public as well as compliance in programme performance evaluations. In this, there are three interested bodies: (i) those requiring a successfully managed environment such as the public; (ii) those responsible to carry-out and monitor the programmes and regulate humans and their activities as mandated by government such as administrators and regulators, and (iii) those implementing the management measures. Here, examples from Europe and North America but with relevance to all maritime states are used to emphasise that management success encompasses a well-defined planning cycle with a vision achieved *as the result of* objectives being met *leading to* actions carried out *leading to* outputs produced *leading to* outcomes achieved.

1. Introduction

This journal has long published papers advocating ocean and coastal management measures and approaches but these have led us to the question in the title of this paper which requires several aspects to be interrogated: What do we mean by management? Who is the ‘we’ that manages ‘whom’, ‘what’ and ‘where’? What do we mean by success? and How do we ‘know’ when it has been achieved? On a basic level, management is the process of completing a task that is required for efficiently and effectively achieving the goals of an organisation (Oshogbunu et al., 2022). Here, we view the marine environment as an entity needing to be successfully and sustainably managed to achieve the overall aim(s) decided by society in both natural and societal terms, including managed human interaction with (and impact on) the environment (Bryant and Wilson, 1998; Steger, 2000). Societal demands and wishes are translated into ‘public policy’ which is derived from

governance which in turn directs environmental management.

Governance is regarded here as the framework by which an entity (country, company or organisation) is directed and controlled; hence, at a country level it includes the sum of policies, politics (including parliamentary action), public administration and legislation; plans and programmes should then achieve these policies using technical measures (Cormier et al., 2022a; Glavovic, 2024; Haugen et al., 2024). As governance is broader but an integral part of management, it applies to governing the political, economic and societal realms (Glavovic, 2024). Marine management then operationalises governance and should encompass both the public and private realms with government implementing policies leading to laws which then produce rules and regulations (Glavovic, 2024). Private marine industries, in turn, must work within these to include operational aspects in order to have economically and societally successful and sustainable businesses. As such there is the need considered in this review to determine, with respect to

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marine management, who can make decisions, who has the authority to act and who is accountable for the performance of the country, company or organisation (see CGI, 2025).

In this context, Ecosystem-based management (EBM) and an Ecosystem-based approach (to management) are integrated ways of managing human activities that consider the entire ecosystem including humans (Kirkfeldt, 2019). The overall management goal is to achieve healthy, clean, productive and resilient marine ecosystems, which can support nature and provide humans with the services, goods and benefits upon which we depend (Borja et al., 2013; Elliott, 2023). This goal requires a spatial and temporal approach encompassing: (a) acknowledging connections between features, (b) cumulative impacts, and (c) multiple objectives (Borja et al., 2024; Piet et al., 2023; Papadopoulou et al., 2025). This mirrors the implementation of holistic instruments such as the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (European Commission, 2008, 2017a). This includes marine pressures and activities, both physico-chemical (e.g. contaminants, litter, and energy generation) and biological (e.g. the introduction of non-indigenous species, pathogens, genetically modified species and extraction of species), which are best managed by input controls (i.e. by stopping their entry or their removal after entry). They are not strictly manageable through spatial and temporal distribution controls (defined below) unlike physical pressures, such as infilling from physical structures, abrasion and erosion.

Such pressures, and others such as biological removal by fisheries, need defined output controls (such as ‘maximum sustainable yield’ for fishing, or environmental quality standards and guidelines) as the policy benchmark of success. Hence, we primarily interrogate these aspects against the question posed by the title of this paper to inform those involved in marine management. We aim to indicate both what is now done but also what needs to be done to improve marine management. This is especially against the background of increasing urbanisation and industrialization of coasts and oceans regardless of precise past and present political philosophies; although we include lessons from business and governance, any discussion of the influences of political ideologies, from neoliberalism to environmentalism, is left to more dedicated works (e.g. Breslow, 2015).

2. Types of management – treating the environment like an organisation, a business or a nation

Firstly, it is valuable to learn lessons for environmental management from other types of management (Table 1). Business management often refers to business structure rather than process and aims to reach the organizational goals established by an executive body (Anthony and Dearden, 1980; Smyth et al., 2019; Stimpson et al., 2024; Dunn, 2018). The ‘Executive’, the highest level which establishes strategic goals, then mandates ‘Management’ to develop objectives to achieve those goals via controls on human and financial resources; thereby effectively and efficiently delivering day-to-day operations to produce expected outcomes. This requires embedded hierarchical authority for

Table 1
Definitions of business, economic and technology management.

Business management	Economic management	Technology management
The process of planning, organising, directing and controlling the activities of a business or organisation to achieves its goals and objectives; it involves overseeing all aspects of a business from finance and operations to marketing and human resources.	The management of the resources, finances, income and expenditure of a community, business enterprise, etc., to achieve budget objectives and optimise costs and benefits.	This includes the strategy, governance, operations and innovation to manage the technological resources effectively to achieve goals and remain competitive in industry.

decision-making (Cormier et al., 2022a) involving goals, objectives and expected outcomes including managing processes, economics and technologies (Table 1); however, there is also the need to include environmental, cultural, social and legal considerations (Elliott, 2013). Clear goals and objectives are needed to determine whether the policies for these types of management, which may be public, corporate or even individual, are met.

Given the above comments, we contend that *the marine environment should be managed as a complex organisation with its own inputs and outputs, ‘aims and objectives’ (to maintain and be maintained), interactions with internal and external players (including natural and societal forces), and controls from inside and outside.*

Marine EBM is globally recognized as the best practice for managing multiple human activities and their resulting pressures (Haugen et al., 2024). Despite the progress worldwide, there are still ambiguities and impediments to implement effective EBM involving: governance, stakeholder engagement, uncertainty in understanding EBM, technology and data, communication and marketing (Haugen et al., 2024; Cormier, 2024). EBM can be regarded as a hierarchy and process for a decision to be made based on a set of principles of policy goals, programme objectives and operational expected outcomes (Cormier et al., 2017; Link and Browman, 2017; Glavovic, 2024); this system is created by a hierarchy analogous to managing a business or even a country but these lead to the question here: *how do we know when marine management has been successful?*

EBM not only involves decision-making processes and tools but who in a business, statutory body or government has been given the authority to make decisions. Business-based and government-based management (Table 2) have hierarchical parallels to make top-down decisions at strategic, management, operational and accountability levels, as well as bottom-up operational and management levels. This requires managing human and financial resources to achieve the expected objectives and outcomes.

As indicated above, all types of management require both management control and operational control to which can be added strategic planning (Table 2). Hence, it is illustrative to tackle the question posed here for the marine environment using experience from Europe and North America but with relevance for all maritime states.

Marine management relies on a cause-consequence-response continuum where prevention, mitigation and/or compensation actions are proposed, adopted and achieved to prevent or even tolerate causes of the risk of adverse consequences. Mitigation reduces the risk, such as by sewage treatment, and compensation may be financial (e.g. paying fish farmers for losses due to pollution), compensating a habitat lost (e.g. by creating biodiversity offsets and remediation), or compensating a resource (e.g., by restocking or replanting) (Elliott et al., 2016).

The causes of change to be managed are usually human demands via marine activities (as sectors such as shipping, fishing, energy extraction, etc.), the consequences are the overall pressures and effects on both the natural and social systems (Elliott et al., 2020) and the management responses control all actors, places and actions (Cormier et al., 2022a). Those responses, especially regulatory frameworks, need to be horizontally-integrated across all the sectors and conservation strategies, and vertically-integrated from the local to global levels (Cormier et al., 2022a). Horizontally-integrating technical actions includes spatial and temporal distribution controls, such as treating effluents with discharge limits, to permit activities within conservation management strategies for vulnerable ecosystem components and species. This complexity requires that the marine environment should be regarded as a complex social-ecological system suitable for a systems analysis approach (Elliott et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2025).

3. Who is the ‘we’ in question?

Determining the marine environmental organizational hierarchy requires clarity about the ‘we’ in our title – it can be any one of: the

Table 2
Types of management control (expanded from Malcolmson et al., 2016).

Control	Business-Based	Government-based
Strategic planning – the process of deciding the goals of the organisation and the broad strategies that are to be used in attaining these goals.	Depending on governance structure of the business enterprise, the Chair of the Board of Directors has the authority to make decisions for the organisation when it comes to establishing goals and strategic plans in counsel with the Board of Directors.	Depending on the configuration of legislative, executive and judicial branches of a government, the head of the legislative branch (e.g. the Supreme Court or Parliamentary Authority*) has the authority to make decisions for the country when it comes to establishing goals and strategic plans in counsel with the legislative branch.
Management control – the process by which management ensures that the organisation carries out its strategies effectively and efficiently.	The Chief Executive Officer has the authority to decide how best to manage effectively and efficiently the activities of the organisation to produce outcomes in line with the goals and strategic plans established by the Chair of the Board of Directors	The head of the Executive branch of the government, (e.g. the Prime Minister in Canada and the UK) has the authority to decide how best to manage effectively and efficiently the plans and programmes of administrations to produce outcomes that relate to the goals and strategic plans established by the head of state.
Operational control – the day-to-day process of assuring that specific tasks are carried out effectively and efficiently.	The senior managers of administrative units are authorised to decide how best to structure the operational delivery of programme outputs to give the outcomes established by the Chief Executive Officer.	As part of the executive branch of government, ministers or departmental secretaries have the authority to decide how best to structure the operational delivery of plan and programme outputs to create the outcomes established by the executive branch

*<https://learn.parl.ca/understanding-comprendre/en/canada-system-of-government/the-branches-of-government/> Each one has separate powers and responsibilities that are defined in the Constitution: the legislative branch passes laws, the executive implements them, and the judiciary interprets them. Under the authority delegated or bestowed by the Head of State or the Monarch as in Canada and the United Kingdom, Parliament passes laws that establishes ‘why’ societal goals are to be reached for the country. The executive branch implements plans and programmes through their administrations that establishes ‘which’ objectives are to be achieved to reach these goals as well as regulate ‘how’ activities are to be conducted to achieve the objectives within the delegation of authorities by law. The judicial branch rules on the interpretation of the law when interpretation differ between the parties involved. The judiciary does not govern, manage, or regulate activities.

activity operator/developer (the body needing to be regulated), regulator (the body performing the regulation) or stakeholder (anybody affected by the decisions taken) and ultimately the public and their elected representatives. As such, asking this question aligns with the similar sentiment of the UN Ocean Decade (<https://oceandecade.org>) which aims for ‘the science we need for the ocean we want’ to encompass all stakeholders. For national or regional governance, regarding whether strategic plans have reached their goals, this would be the head of state, legislature or parliament. In the case of goals, plans and programmes implemented by administrations, ‘we’ is the ‘competent authority’ that has been delegated through legal instruments (e.g. in EU Directives). All aspects of environment, economy, technology and society, will include relevant stakeholders who again could be ‘statutory’ (i.e. formed from underpinning legislation such as an Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)) or non-statutory in the case of the public or Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs).

The ‘we’ includes different levels of decision-making from

international, regional and national public policy perspectives. This involves those legally competent bodies delegated to authorize, licence and permit activities, e.g., UN Signatories, the EU Member States, the public for State legislative and executive branches, stakeholders for mandated administrations, and individual regulators.

In essence, public administrations or ministries develop plans and programmes to achieve objectives reflecting the goals or aims of strategic policies and plans established by legislatures or parliaments. Using the European MSFD (European Commission, 2008) as an example, Annex II requires identifying EU Member State competent authorities involved in the assessment of Good Environmental Status (GES) and then implementing Programmes of Measures (PoM) to achieve GES (Borja et al., 2013). This is the same in Canada, where various competent authorities are mandated to manage pressures generated by marine activities and including marine protection and conservation (Canada, 1996).

The ‘we’ includes the competent marine authorities as well as those managing land-based activities to address the land-sea interface; for example, as required by the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD; European Union, 2014), and the Water Framework Directive (WFD, European Commission, 2000). The competent authorities, informed by scientific knowledge, research and monitoring, as well as the wishes of society, are accountable to administer the legislation and policies of their national governments. In turn, in the case of the EU, the national governments are accountable to Brussels (and hence will be subject to infraction proceedings if they breach EU legislation and so incur fines set by the European Court of Justice (ECJ)). The regulated parties (e.g. a marine industry) must comply with national legal instruments under the authority of government-appointed bodies such as an Environmental Protection Agency (EPA in the US or Environment Agency in England) or the Office of Environmental Responsibility in the UK (set up to police environmental performance following Brexit).

A competent authority is bound by the legislation and policies to administer such plans and programmes which rely on monitoring indicators and the criteria (e.g., for the MSFD listed in European Commission (2017a) or in Canada (Cormier et al., 2022b.)). The competent authority requires fit-for-purpose scientific information to report on the outcomes of plans and programmes. That science may be descriptive, predictive or even uncertain, hence the need for advisors such as ACOM (Advisory Committee) at the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), the Canadian Science Advisory Secretariat (CSAS) in Canada (DFO, 2023; Canada, 2000; CSTA, 1999) or the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission (USNRC, 1981). These need to be clear about the required policy-relevant knowledge and the sequence when science advice is requested.

Not all relevant bodies have the same view of success in management: (a) regulators will require that legislation and licences were followed and their aims achieved; (b) environmental-NGOs may want natural areas protected irrespective of social consequences, and (c) the wider stakeholders may regard economic benefits, employment, human welfare and, perhaps lastly, environmental protection, as the indications of success. For example, ensuring that a beach has ‘sea, sun, sand and a bacterial quality suitable for bathing’ may satisfy tourists irrespective of whether there are any natural habitats and species in the area.

4. What and where are we managing?

Management is required directly or indirectly for all components of the cause-consequence-response continuum, as exemplified through the DAPSI(W)R(M) (pronounced *dap-see-worm*) framework and its antecedents (Patrício et al., 2016; Elliott et al., 2017). Management therefore has to directly control the Drivers (as basic human needs), Activities and Pressures, to prevent the State changes (on the natural system) and the Impacts (on human Welfare) using Responses (through management Measures). Those pressures, defined as the mechanisms of change, may be *endogenic* (i.e. created within a jurisdiction of the management area in

which their causes and consequences are managed, for example fisheries or energy generation), or *exogenic* in which the causes may be outside the jurisdiction of the management area but the consequences are within that area and so require managing (such as the results of sea-level rise due to climate change).

Ultimately, management must minimise the risk to both the natural and human systems (Cormier et al., 2019). However, a risk will never be acceptable to everyone and so regulations and standards are needed to set tolerance levels to reduce risk to As Low As Reasonably Practicable (ALARP) (Timms, 2006; IEC/ISO, 2019). Risk is never zero and, within reason, levels of risk are tolerated when developing and implementing management controls or measures (Baybutt, 2014). For example, discharging sewage into the sea is often tolerated as a cheap way of removing waste and has even been summarised in the adage ‘*the solution to pollution is dilution*’; this relies on the ability of coastal areas to disperse, degrade and assimilate the waste even though the general public are aware of the risks to both the natural system and to human health, especially with regard to bathing beaches. However, the risk of not achieving policy objectives depends on the effectiveness of management measures on the permitted activities and pressures together with sustainability goals (Blanz et al., 2024).

Successful management of the causes of change centres on the nature of marine environmental hazards and the risks emanating from them. While hazards occur naturally or as the result of human action (or inaction), they become risks when affecting something valued by society (Cormier et al., 2019; Elliott and Kennish, 2024). For example, a tsunami is a natural hazard which becomes a risk to coastal communities with more severe consequences when coastal protection by mangroves is removed to make way for fishponds (Wolanski and Elliott, 2015); as a second example, adding chemicals to the sea is an anthropogenic hazard which then becomes a risk when the chemicals are taken up by seafood gathered during fishing. Natural hazards cannot be managed, only their consequences.

5. What do we mean by ‘knowing success’ in management?

In business, successful management is reaching the business objectives, the economic and societal requirements or, at very least, not being prosecuted, i.e. not breaching the requirements set by the regulator. This is no different for the marine environment. ‘Knowing’ success in management, requires SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and time-bounded) key risk, control and performance indicators being framed from legislation and policies established by the competent authority; for example, an EPA would set those indicators and require compliance by a marine industry. Hence, the competent authority ultimately determines the success of its plans and programmes by monitoring indicators of their outputs and outcomes established in regulation or as environmental targets (Cormier et al., 2022a,b). This centres on setting well-defined aims (or a vision) and objectives each with their own indicators and targets, accompanied by monitoring, and consequently determining whether the management (and legal and societal) success implications of these indicators (or targets) are or are not being met.

6. How to measure successful management by types of indicators related to monitoring?

Policy-relevant and policy-defined indicators and objectives should be SMART and so more likely to be legally and operationally defensible; these must relate to what management is needed and whether that management was successful (i.e. following the adage that ‘*you cannot manage unless you can measure*’). The indicators must be specific to the objective as the outcome being sought (e.g. contaminant levels in fish sufficiently low to ensure safe seafood). If not specific, they will not be measurable and we will not be able to ascertain if we are achieving the policy objective realistically and within the mandated time.

By definition and practice, marine activities should be officially allowed (i.e. sanctioned/licenced/permitted) but a licence can contain only legally defensible measures; for example, monitoring is needed to confirm that a contaminant in wastewater should not exceed x ppm or the number of sewage pathogens discharged as y per 100 ml (Elliott and Wither, 2024). In contrast, a clause such as ‘the biodiversity of the area should not be adversely affected’ cannot be included in a licence as it could be subject to challenge given the differing number of ways and factors in measuring biodiversity change. Furthermore, a change in biodiversity may be so ill-defined that it is unable to distinguish which activity and pressure requires management. Environmental quality guidelines can provide either a supplementary or an alternative basis for monitoring (Cormier et al., 2022b).

Policy-relevant indicators for the controls used are needed to ‘know’ if management of human activities is producing the output and outcomes established in policy, i.e. ‘success’. The history of administering legislation and policies in a planning, regulatory and auditing role, shows that the competent bodies rely on policy-relevant indicators to ‘know’ for reporting on the output and outcomes of plans and programmes. Table 3 gives examples of the types of measures which can be used as the final success criteria in management. Other possible and potential indicators include the Essential Ocean and Biodiversity Variables (although these may be too general for operational use) (Lumbierres et al., 2024), Business Performance Indicators and Success Criteria, means of setting and meeting goals (synonymous with setting the aims, objectives and vision), and types of outputs versus outcomes (respectively the deliverable and the main achievement of the aims). Such measures would also ensure that a country can achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) (Cormier and Elliott, 2017; Ryabinin, 2020; Cormier et al., 2021; Andriamahefazafy et al., 2022).

Table 3

Types of measures as the final criteria of success in management (developed from Cormier et al., 2022a). (Acronyms are explained in the text above).

Measure	Definition	Examples for marine areas
OKR – Objectives & Key Results	a goal-setting framework that helps individuals and teams focus on the most important aspects, align their efforts, and track progress towards achieving their objectives	In the case of the EU MSFD, the objective is to achieve GES and the Key result would be achieving it as shown by indicators; however, these terms were not used explicitly in the legislation
KPI – Key Performance Indicators	quantifiable measures of performance over time for a specific objective. KPIs provide targets at which to aim, milestones to measure progress, and information for better decision-making	MSFD 2008/56 Annex I descriptors of good environmental status; UN SDG targets, but as yet these are aspirational goals and visions and need to be made SMART to show successful management
KCI – Key Control Indicators	metrics showing the extent to which a given operational risk control is meeting its intended objectives	MSFD 2008/56 Annex VI Output controls for each of the Table 2a entries in MSFD 2017/845: Anthropogenic pressures on the marine environment; these must be SMART to be operational and informed by the Programmes of Measures for the MSFD and other Directives
KRI – Key Risk Indicators	to provide an early signal of increasing potential risk exposures to the continuation of the activity or project. They differ from a KPI which measure how well something is being done while KRI indicate the possibility of future adverse impact	Table 2 in MSFD 2017/845 Anthropogenic pressures, uses and human activities in or affecting the marine environment; these must be SMART to be operational; this is shown by the risk and hazard typology (Elliott and Kennish, 2024).

7. The central role of monitoring in determining management success

Once the aims, objectives, targets and thresholds have been pre-defined with accompanying indicators then these require true monitoring, i.e. analysis against pre-defined values (Borja and Elliott, 2021; Cormier et al., 2022a,b). For example, monitoring demonstrating achieving or maintaining good or acceptable biodiversity status shows that marine management is successful. This especially includes monitoring for compliance with licence conditions, operational monitoring by industry, and surveillance and condition monitoring by the nature conservation bodies (Elliott and Wither, 2024).

Adequate monitoring requires cost-effectively obtaining appropriate data and information of relevant ecological components (i.e. what may be regarded as the ‘need-to-know’ versus ‘nice-to-know’). Academics may think it is ‘nice’ to have a lot of information, but regulators should decide what is ‘needed’ for management decisions and so having skills and ensuring data are fit-for-purpose (Elliott et al., 2020; Oliver et al., 2021). Furthermore, although academic studies may give much information showing management success for components, in the case of the MSFD, these are inadmissible by Member States, are not regarded as ‘official’ information and are unlikely to meet MSFD guidelines (European Commission, 2008, 2017a, 2017b). Hence, countries are required to designate their ‘official’ data and information, i.e. those to be used in officially-accepted assessments.

Monitoring should indicate the need to make, or result of making correct decisions, i.e. an ultimate signal of success in management. This requires: (1) identifying information (or data) relevant to the anticipated decision; (2) systematically acquiring this information, and (3) rigorously analysing the data acquired (Elliott and Wither, 2024). This requires a logical systems analysis framework (Smith et al., 2025), i.e. ‘a directed process for the orderly and timely acquisition and investigation of specific system information pertinent to a given decision’ (USNRC, 1981). Hence, the emphasis (at least initially) should be on the process (i.e., acquiring information) and not on the product (i.e., the system model as the conceptual representation governing our thinking). This emphasis is necessary as, in the absence of a directed, manageable, and disciplined process, the resultant system model will be inadequate.

Furthermore, there is the need to decide what information is essential and desirable to a given decision before the data are gathered (i.e. the ‘need-to-know’). Unfortunately, such rigour is often not followed and unnecessary data are collected (what may be termed a ‘helicopter survey’ (Elliott and Wither, 2024)). For example, collecting zooplankton data near a proposed offshore windfarm, albeit interesting, is unlikely to give relevant information for decision-making. This is due to the type of pressures generated by the windfarm contrasting with plankton dynamics which are highly variable related to the scale of the proposed effect (the so-called ‘signal to noise’ ratio). In this case, monitoring is unlikely to signify success of management decisions and illustrates that it should be rigorously governed by the management objectives (e.g.

Franco et al., 2015).

While monitoring is required to demonstrate the need for or the success of management, it may start with one topic or component, but academic curiosity or associated commercial interests may expand the monitoring out of the ‘need-to-know’ into the ‘nice-to-know’. While this may yield interesting information (as with the zooplankton example), it may not relate to the management problem in hand (USNRC, 1981). Decision-making conceptually is shown in Fig. 1 where Block A represents what is accepted as certified reality which then, through scientific field, experimental or literature investigation, leads to a model (conceptual, empirical or deterministic) (Block B). Further iteration then leads to Block C of inferred or proven conclusions providing the basis for a management decision which is communicated and implemented by the outputs and outcomes. Hence, the management decision is a direct outcome of the model which, if wrong, so will be the decision. Clearly, then, the greatest emphasis should be to ensure that the system model provides an accurate representation of reality.

8. Can management success cover all social and natural features?

Actions for successful and sustainable environmental management have been described as the 10-tenets, to be: 1) ecologically sustainable, 2) technologically feasible, 3) economically viable, 4) legally permissible, 5) administratively achievable, 6) socially desirable/tolerable, 7) politically expedient, 8) ethically defensible/morally correct, 9) culturally inclusive, and 10) effectively communicable (Elliott, 2013). This is partly analogous to the business-orientated PESTLE approach in which a business operates in a Political, Economic, Social, Technical and Legal Environment (i.e. omitting natural environmental aspects) (Elliott and Wither, 2024). Cormier and Kannen (2019) emphasise that assessing these 10-tenets is central to marine risk management and spatial planning.

The tenets 1–5 are quantitative and can be obtained as an amount or factually from government and other sources, whereas 6–10 are qualitative and can only be indicated as narratives, possibly based on stakeholder interviews. Furthermore, risk identification and analysis do not apply to the tenets 4, 5, 7 and 8 which are mostly within the realms of parliaments and government and show the importance of legislation, policy, administrations and human rights. The competent marine planning authority is unlikely to have the mandate to change these four tenets, which may fall under different competent authorities, but would require the developer to include them in an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) (Elliott and Wither, 2024). Successful management by the competent authority should reflect an ecologically sustainable solution whereas the developer will need an economically viable and technologically feasible solution, for example using a BATNEEC (Best Available Technology Not Exceeding Excessive Cost) approach (Elliott and Wither, 2024).

Sustainable and successful marine management requires all parties

Fig. 1. – Relationships between the real and inferred outcomes (greatly modified from USNRC, 1981).

to be consulted during the planning process, but this may not always be the case and whereas statutory consultees should be included (e.g. EPA, local municipalities), NGOs may not. All social and natural features (i.e., all tenets) should fall within a competent authority which by definition would have a decision-making and regulatory mandate; however, missing any relevant stakeholders may prevent successful management.

Mandates can be given to administer social programmes, law-making processes, or broader government policies without the delegation of a 'competent authority'. Therefore, the 'we' in our thesis may not always be a competent authority but may be a government auditor, parliamentary committee, other public organisation, or even a court judge in litigation cases. For example, reflecting the management hierarchy, the marine planner makes recommendations to the senior authority (e.g. minister on behalf of a head of state or at least a planning inspector with quasi-judicial powers) once the planning process and consultation are completed (Elliott and Wither, 2024).

The 'know' part of the challenge addressed here would be identified by 'Monitoring and Review' which implies that all tenets are monitored and reported against quantitative or qualitative indicators. These indicators and data from public surveys may be reported by national statistics collected by census departments, a key and mandatory step in the international standard ISO 31000 (ISO, 2018).

The environmental success of public policies will be indicated by a general review from the Commissioner for the Environment (Canada), the Office for Environmental Responsibility (UK) or the European Commission. Although the EU MSFD provides methodological standards and indicators for EU Member States to report their GES (i.e. the environmentally/ecologically sustainable tenet), the indicators for the other tenets would have to be found in national statistics from business, economic or health ministries simply because an environmental competent authority would not necessarily collect such statistics. Furthermore, indicators generated through scientific research could be key performance indicators for a competent authority to 'know management has been successful' (Teixeira et al., 2016). However, using and reporting such indicators needs approval by the relevant competent authorities.

As suggested here, there are constraints on what information can be used to demonstrate successful marine management. From a compliance perspective under the legal authority, regulations, standards and guidelines used to manage human activities typically have pre-set indicators as well as nominated sampling and analytical methods to be used; for example, the CEN method standards referred to in annexes of the EU Directives (<https://www.cencenelec.eu/european-standardization/european-standards/>). The regulator as well as the person/industry/activity that must comply with such cannot legally use other indicators, sampling or analytical methods. This applies to environmental pollution regulations as well as fish and seafood safety regulations (Canada, 2024; CCME, 2024; AOAC, 2023) and scientists involved in reporting to competent authorities should use such accredited methods (Cormier et al., 2022b).

Typically, indicators, monitoring and methods used for regulatory compliance as well as plan and programme performance are developed by scientific and technical experts through formalized technical processes (AOAC, 2023). Other indicators (e.g. those developed academically) would not be admissible in such legislative settings without a formalized advisory process and especially independent AQC/QA (Analytical Quality Control/ Quality Assurance, Elliott et al., 2020) as in ISO standards. Such a formal approach is necessary as it is not possible for policy and technical analysts working in government administrations to analyse and understand the many published scientific discipline studies, data and methods; hence, such standards give confidence in the results. Despite this, management success relies on subject matter experts to peer review the literature, data and methods to formulate the advice requested by the competent authority. Examples include the Advisory Committee of ICES, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and national examples such as the Canadian Scientific Advisory Secretariat or the US National Academy of Sciences (ICES,

2024; IPCC, 2024; CSAS, 2024). This requires and creates a rigorous analysis of the scientific evidence to reach a consensus in preparing the advice (Lindblom and Cohen, 1979; Gluckman, 2016; Kenny et al., 2017; Galland et al., 2018).

It is emphasised here that success in management is especially shown by many types of indicators (Teixeira et al., 2016; Elliott and Kennish, 2024) including those explicitly used in regulations and standards which should include the sampling design and testing method; these indicators are typically diagnostic as well as used for licence compliance. Based on the authority legally delegated to a regulator, the latter can only state that the results comply with the regulation or the standard and does not have the authority to interpret them out of context. Finally, some required indicators are mostly descriptive and/or use a large variety of methods and thus are difficult for use in decision-making but can be used in decision-support (Montenero et al., 2021).

9. Output controls are needed as environmental targets in defining management success

Central to management success are *Output controls*, which can be considered as the key control indicators for the effectiveness and reliability of the *input controls* and the spatial and temporal *distribution controls* (Table 4). These controls are used to manage human activities (e.g. as listed in European Commission, 2017a) which are the key risk indicators while those for the MSFD descriptors for GES are the key performance indicators (Cormier et al., 2022a). In the case of the MSFD, Output controls for the pressures listed in European Commission (2017a) are needed as well as environmental targets to determine the success in meeting GES.

The standards necessary for successful management should set tolerance levels, i.e. the permitted amount of perturbation in the target component (e.g. a medium, species, stock, individual or habitat), as defined by the output control. Then monitoring of the indicator should have a confidence level showing change (the 'signal') over and above the sampling 'noise' (the inherent variability of the component) to lead to the prescribed action when exceeded. Such monitoring requires AQC/QA procedures to ensure that the sampling and analytical methods will give the expected precision and accuracy (Franco et al., 2015; Elliott et al., 2020), thereby reducing the possibility that management action is not taken due to a false positive. An output control tied to a regulatory limit, a standard or even a guideline requires a much lower level of uncertainty than an environmental target (Stelzenmüller et al., 2020).

10. What are the repercussions of success and failure in marine management?

While hazards may occur due to human or natural events (Elliott and Kennish, 2024), human actions creating risks that endanger human lives, livelihoods and wellbeing should be regarded as management failure. General risk management guidelines and standards agree that risk is tolerated even though it may be assumed that any risk is unacceptable to at least one actor. Therefore, risk tolerance may include trade-offs which fall to the executive, legislative, or judicial branches of government and are central to policymaking, i.e. protecting nature and society from such risks is the central aim of environmental management and, indeed, all governments.

Management success may differ with stakeholder type (Newton and Elliott, 2016, Table 5) and their acceptance of risks related to the 10-tenets. In the typology, the Influencers, Beneficiaries and Affecteds can also be Inputters and Extractors affected by political processes and policymaking; they could try to influence a decision for their own benefit or to avoid being affected by such decision. Furthermore, a stakeholder could appeal to the legislative, executive and judicial branches of government if dissatisfied with an outcome of management; for example, taking court action over a pollution spillage. Again, this is based on risk management principles that any risk is unacceptable, e.g.

Table 4Controls and measures for successful marine management (from the MSFD, [European Commission \(2008\)](#) Annex VI).

- (1) Input controls: management measures that influence the amount of a human activity that is permitted.
- (2) Output controls: management measures that influence the degree of perturbation of an ecosystem component that is permitted.
- (3) Spatial and temporal distribution controls: management measures that influence where and when an activity is allowed to occur.
- (4) Management coordination measures: tools to ensure that management is coordinated.
- (5) Measures to improve the traceability, where feasible, of marine pollution.
- (6) Economic incentives: management measures which make it in the economic interest of those using the marine ecosystems to act in ways which help to achieve the good environmental status objective.
- (7) Mitigation and remediation tools: management tools which guide human activities to restore damaged components of marine ecosystems.
- (8) Communication, stakeholder involvement and raising public awareness.

Table 5The stakeholder typology with an indication of its management success (adapted from [Newton and Elliott, 2016](#)).

Stakeholder type	Management success is when:
Inputters – those putting materials or infrastructure into the seas	Their business is successful in economic or societal terms, they have not breached any licences, and not suffered reputational damage
Extractors – those removing physical, chemical or biological material or space from the marine system	Their business is successful in economic or societal terms, they have not breached any licences, and not suffered reputational damage
Regulators – those controlling the extractors and inputters, i.e. the competent authorities	The regulations have been followed within overall governance (defined above); that they have succeeded without resorting to legal sanctions
Affectees – those affected by the materials placed in and extracted from the seas, the activities and their regulation	Their quality of life and welfare has not been impeded (and hopefully is enhanced) by the users of the system
Beneficiaries – those benefitting from all the activities in the sea and their management	They benefit from the economic, societal and welfare benefits of the outputs of the activities as well as the preservation of a natural environment which can accommodate the human activities without deterioration
Influencers – those aiming to influence the users (and abusers) of the seas and those introducing or implementing policies and legislation	That they can see the benefits of their influence in a better educated population, an acceptance of policies, and/or in short-, medium- and long-term planning; however, the further away the science is from policy puts science in a never-ending influencer role

Inputters and Extractors that are unlikely to be satisfied with the limits imposed, the Influencers not agreeing that their influence produced what they intended, the Beneficiaries that did not get what they were expecting, and the Affectees that ended up being affected negatively by a decision. All of this is prevented by good marine environmental governance and management ([Glavovic, 2024](#)) - hence, for the Legislative Branch, management success is shown by the necessary legislation being created, for the Executive Branch it is that policies are achieved, and for the Judicial Branch it is that the laws are upheld. In EU terms, a new Directive could be created, enacted by Member States in line with their government policy and, with a failure to comply, either the state being reported to the European Court of Justice for infraction proceedings or an industry being prosecuted in national courts.

Legally-supported licences, authorisations or permits are used to control the Inputters and Extractors to ensure that their activities are environmentally sound while the Executive branch of government is required to create societal benefits. Of course, an Affectee can always take court action to challenge as unfair a judgement based on legislation, government programmes or industry activity harming the environment. Aided by public pressure, the Regulators (as the competent authorities) should ensure the 10-tenets are achieved to control marine activities.

Management success depends on controls on activities through licence conditions which will be on a pass/fail basis, including environmental compliance targets related to overall policy; for example, the

microbe concentration in a marine sewage discharge staying within a limit on a given number of occasions in a bathing season ([Elliott and Wither, 2024](#)). Hence, success in marine management requires setting output controls and environmental targets as regulations or policies and then imposing penalties for infringement (see [Selkoe et al., 2015](#)). In contrast, in this example, the sewerage company business success will have economic and other criteria and governance success will be based on achieving the overall policy. However, at the highest level, for marine activities, the number of prosecutions, number of fines, changes to business practices and lack of economic success due to environmental constraints could be regarded as a failure of management.

11. Case-studies of success or progress in environmental management

Case 1. Pollution reduction in the Nervión estuary (Basque Country) and recovery of its ecosystem services

It is of value to use real examples of the above points to show success in environmental management. The Basque Country, northern Spain, is a small region containing 12 small estuaries (2–22 km in length) and 150 km of coast ([Borja et al., 2006a](#)). Intense industrialization from the mid-19th Century, especially with iron mining, steel, paper mills and chemical industries led to a population increase, and a subsequent high land-claim in the estuaries, for port development, and human and industrial settlement ([Cearreta et al., 2004](#)). This led to intertidal habitat losses of 15–88% per estuary, with many human pressures such as nutrient discharges, water and sediment pollution by metals and organic compounds, water abstraction, dredging, shoreline reinforcement, intertidal losses, moorings (ports) and the introduction of alien species ([Borja et al., 2006a](#)). Maximum degradation, with habitat and biodiversity losses, as well as high levels of pollution, occurred around the 1970s–1980s, with anoxic and azoic areas in some estuaries, especially in the Nervión estuary ([Borja et al., 2016](#)). This estuary became one of the most polluted estuaries in Europe from its harbour development and around one million inhabitants ([Cearreta et al., 2004](#)) indicating a failure of environmental management or, alternatively, the acceptance that degradation is a price worth paying for industrial and urban development.

The trajectory over time in this estuary indicates interactions between ecosystem components, their degradation and the recovery of ecosystem services and societal benefits by restoring the habitat quality after taking management actions ([Fig. 2](#)). Illustrating this trajectory required comprehensive monitoring which started in 1989, thus increasing understanding of system interactions, including biological functioning ([García-Barcina et al., 2006](#); [Cajaraville et al., 2016](#)). Several main management actions have driven the recovery of the system, such as diversion of discharges and the start of water treatment in the late 1980s, the closure in 1995 of the most polluting company in the estuary, starting secondary treatment in 2001, and connecting the whole population to water treatment ([Borja et al., 2016, Fig. 2](#)).

These management actions restored the physico-chemical conditions of the system, showing increasing dissolved oxygen, from the hypoxic-anoxic situation in the inner part of the estuary, when the monitoring started. The SMART target of the clean-up plan, of reaching 60% oxygen

Fig. 2. Nervión estuary recovery, after different management actions and the clean-up programme, on different ecosystem components and cultural benefits such as bathing and recreational fishing (Updated and modified from Borja et al., 2010). Colours indicate the level of degradation or recovery. Key to indicators: M-AMBI: multivariate AMBI; H': Shannon's diversity; AFI: AZTI's Fish Index; MPN: most probable number; recre: recreational. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

saturation in the water column (García-Barcina et al., 2006), was achieved when the secondary treatment started, and the saturation now reaches 80–100% (Fig. 2). The severe pollution was reduced progressively, especially in the water column, but still with moderate pollution in sediments (Borja et al., 2016).

The previous anoxic sediments of the inner estuary prevented soft-bottom macroinvertebrate settlement, and the area was azoic until 1997 (Borja et al., 2006b); however, after 20 years of progressive clean-up and recovery, the system has achieved a good ecological status as shown by the indicator M-AMBI for macroinvertebrates (Fig. 2). In the outer part of the estuary, less affected by pollution and the only part with natural hard-substratum, the recovery of rocky benthic communities took at least 14 years (Díez et al., 2009; Bustamante, 2013). Demersal communities (fish and crustaceans) were absent due to the absence of oxygen, but then recovered when prey was available, as detected by the AZTI Fish Index (Uriarte and Borja, 2009) (Fig. 2). Seabirds, in this case cormorants, followed the recovery of fish, increasing to over 400 breeding pairs, thereby denoting successful management of the whole ecosystem.

The recovery of the different ecosystem components has recently been accompanied by the recovery of societal goods and benefits provided by ecosystem services (Elliott, 2023). An increased biological value was followed by the recovery of cultural ecosystem benefits, namely recreational fishing and use of beaches for sunbathing and sports, thereby giving environmental, social and economic benefits (Pascual et al., 2012; Pouso et al., 2018a–c, 2019, 2021). As a metric of management success, an interdisciplinary approach then created a single, integrated evaluation of the recovery of the services and benefits in the estuary (Pouso et al., 2020). Hence, the increased recreational fishing followed the physico-chemical recovery of the system and the

recolonization of the inner estuary by fish (Pouso et al., 2019), with increasing catch weight (Fig. 2). Despite this evidence of management success, 69% of the fishers continue to assume a decreased fish abundance and 36% consider no change in fish species richness (Pouso et al., 2018b). In contrast, 75% of beach users consider that the quality of the water has improved (Fig. 2), and 62% of visitors practice aquatic activities on beaches (Pouso et al., 2018a).

As an economic indication of management success, using the travel cost method, Pouso et al. (2020) showed that beach visitors are willing to spend on average 7.05 € per visit, creating an aggregate access value of 3.5 M€ yr⁻¹. In the case of recreational fishing these values are 449 € yr⁻¹ fisher⁻¹ and 1.1 M€ yr⁻¹, respectively. Considering that the beach maintenance costs 0.67 M€ yr⁻¹, and the wastewater treatment costs 23.7 M€ yr⁻¹, these two societal benefits alone annually cover 100% of the beach maintenance costs and 20% of the water treatment (Pouso et al., 2020). As there are many other ecosystem services and societal benefits not included in those studies (e.g., food provision, carbon sequestration, nursery functions, pollutant cycling, other cultural benefits), the economic benefits of the estuarine restoration will be much higher than the investments over time, also demonstrating management success.

Case 2. The European MSFD as an example of progressive success in management

The MSFD is a comprehensive framework for management strategies with goals, objectives expressed as targets and expected outcomes from output controls. The ultimate success of marine management through MSFD implementation is in reaching the vision of the European Marine Strategy using indicators, programmes of measures and monitoring, and management actions including carrying out ecosystem restoration using eco- and geo-engineering (including Nature-based Solutions). The

outputs are of acceptable submissions to the EC and the outcome is attaining GES in the European seas. More pragmatically, an outcome is also in a Member State not being placed in infraction proceedings before the European Court with a subsequent fine.

The MSFD is enabled by national competent bodies that regulate marine activities using indicators for pressures, state change and impacts on human welfare, i.e. that measure the degree of perturbation of an ecosystem component that has been permitted in regulation (i.e. termed an Output control). These include the criteria and indicators that measure the status of a descriptor that has been established as an environmental target (European Commission, 2008, 2017a). Hence, the competent authority ascertains the 'success' of their plans and programmes by assessment against established outputs and outcomes. Therefore, 'knowing' that success is in achieving an outcome as an overall vision or objective (e.g. 'to achieve clean, healthy, diverse and productive seas') and not just, for example, implementing the Directive by creating a monitoring plan, a programme of measures or a status assessment. Member States must report to the EU, the GES against their output controls in their regulations and the environmental targets they have established using criteria and method standards.

As indicators are required to both inform when management is needed and indicate when it has succeeded, reaching the indicators in MSFD Commission Decision 2017/848 (European Commission, 2017a) shows success in management. Some indicators measure pressures while others measure status with management success being the prevention of the pressures and a maintenance/improvement in the status. This requires a rigorous cause-consequence-response framework and model as shown by the industry-standard Bow-tie analysis (Cormier et al., 2018a, 2019) leading to risk assessment and management strategies.

Marine management, as typified by the MSFD, aims to accommodate many activities and hence assess cumulative or collective pressures influencing GES (Borja et al., 2024), i.e. a main function of the assessments under MSFD Article 8. The EU amendments (European Commission, 2017a, b) increased clarity regarding human activities and pressures and aligned these with indicators.

Using cause, event and consequence analysis, successful management requires a cumulative risk profile linking human activities to pressures to effects on natural and societal marine environmental status (European Commission, 2017a, b; Piet et al., 2023). In illustrating a management response, Cormier et al. (2018b, 2022a) showed that the MSFD Programmes of Measures, input controls and spatial and temporal distribution controls are used to reduce the inputs (chemical, biological and physical substances, litter, and energy) to a level that is below the output control (i.e. the limits to activities). Furthermore, mitigation and remediation tools are used to restore damaged components of marine ecosystems when that damage reflects exceeding the output control (i.e. management has not limited the activities). Thus, the controls are the regulatory and non-regulatory instruments (laws and behaviour) to reduce the risks of collective pressures to a level As Low As Reasonably Practicable (ALARP) below the output control (see Cormier et al., 2018b, 2022a).

It is necessary to quantify the effectiveness of many technical measures, such as pollution controls (Cormier et al., 2022a), in meeting an output control, i.e. successful management. Achieving and maintaining GES not only depends on defining marine protected areas but also on the controls used to manage human activities. This is a key integration consideration for managing activities to reduce cumulative effects (Cormier et al., 2018b, 2019; Stelzenmüller et al., 2020).

Successful marine management relies on setting environmental targets which establish the desired conditions for a particular descriptor of GES based on measurable indicators that in turn determine if the target is achieved. However, scientific, management and operational uncertainty will create greater uncertainty in the objective it is intended to achieve, e.g. a target from Annex IV of the MSFD 2008/56. Some MSFD 2017/848 indicators measure an output control while others measure GES (Table 3). It is of note that, in mirroring the MSFD, Canadian

environmental regulations are mainly used to set output controls in which protection programmes establish codes of practice and standards for the controls.

If GES is not achieved for a given sea area, then a Programme of Measures (PoM) must be implemented to ensure management success. The environmental targets for each MSFD descriptor are ultimately the key performance indicators of the implementation of the PoM. Output controls and environmental targets are policy benchmarks for effective 'management' controls and performance of 'successful' plans and programmes, but they are not threshold indicators to predict impacts on the natural state and human wellbeing.

The European Commission (2017a, b) documents establish indicators needed to measure the level of pressures to determine whether they are reduced to a level related to a specific output control in the original MSFD (European Commission, 2008); hence, marine management success lies in showing that the pressures are not causing adverse effects. The relevant pressures paired with the status indicators (European Commission, 2017a) are needed subsequently to indicate how close national management strategies are to maintaining and achieving GES (European Commission, 2008). Therefore, when types of indicators are already established in policy, they require adequate monitoring related to the policy objectives set by environmental managers to determine if their management strategies are successful. Hence, in the MSFD, SMART objectives are very much the output control and environmental targets. In essence, if the targets are met, the indicators not breached, the Member State not placed in infraction proceedings, and the developer/industry not prosecuted then it can be assumed that management has succeeded.

Figure 3 reinterprets the MSFD in which the desired sequence is given below the starting point from why the Directive is implemented through to where and when it is implemented. Despite this, in our experience, practitioners tend to focus on the practical work without fully considering the overall aims.

12. Discussion, summary and recommendations for the way ahead

This paper started with the need to address the question of 'how do we know that marine management has been successful?' which has led us to conclude that, inherent in the question: the 'Why' is based on policy, the 'What' is based on plans and programmes, and 'How' is based on technical measures. This follows with 'Who' requires that the policy will result in a 'successfully managed environment', 'Who' is 'accountable' for the policy objectives to be achieved, 'Who' is 'mandated' to develop the plans and programmes to achieve the policy objectives, and 'Who' is 'responsible' to regulate those that generate pressures. However, we also should consider 'Who' are those having to implement the technical measures by activities to benefit the other 'Who' bodies that require a successfully managed environment. This includes the competent authorities needing Key Performance Indicators for the policy objectives, Key Risk Indicators for the plans and programmes and Key Control Indicators for the technical measures used in regulatory and non-regulatory programmes.

The conditions for successful and sustainable marine environmental management should be within a strategic planning framework. This requires a well-developed and accepted planning cycle (Fig. 4, inner circle) in which there should be an overall vision for an area based on its aims and objectives. The clockwise completed sequence then requires actions, outputs and outcomes to determine if the vision is achieved. Management can be regarded as being successful if the objectives are met, the actions are carried out, the outputs are produced, the outcomes are achieved and the vision is satisfied – these links are denoted by the red lines. The overriding aims are thus connected to the outcomes but only through following the whole cycle (as shown by both cycles of inner blue lines).

While authorities may mainly focus on the effects and spatial

Fig. 3. The EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) implementation – what should be done (effort decreasing from left to right) and what is done in practice (effort increasing from left to right).. (Acronyms given in text.)

Fig. 4. The planning cycle (inner circle) embedded with the indication of management success (outer 2 circles) (see text for explanation).

planning of both activities and environmental protection, it is necessary to clarify the effectiveness of the controls used to manage activities (Cormier et al., 2022a, b). As indicated in the case of the MSFD, the main ‘controls’ refer to the amount, where and when human activities are permitted while the output controls are about the degree of perturbation that is permitted. These controls relate to regulatory frameworks which should cover all facets of successful and sustainable management; consequently, the way in which the 10-tenets are achieved is indicative of successful marine management (Table 6).

The analysis here has emphasised the need to evaluate fulfilling goals and producing outcomes as measures of management success, but we realise that there will be delays and trade-offs in this between the different players. Hence, we emphasise that there needs to be a greater importance on procedural aspects of management processes such as ensuring effective stakeholder engagement and monitoring followed by

Table 6

– What successful and sustainable marine management looks like in relation to the 10-tenets being achieved (Acronyms are given in the text).

Tenet	Evidence that the tenet is achieved to give successful and sustainable marine management
Ecologically sustainable	The marine, coastal and estuarine areas are in good ecological, environmental, chemical status, e.g. they meet these aspects of the EU Directives.
Economically viable	Financial aspects secured in the long-term for both the planning and implementation of the plan by those charged with sustainably carrying out and manipulating activities; this can include BATNEEC – use of Best Available Technology (in restoration) and even, pragmatically, Not Entailing Excessive Cost, for example waste-water treatment as shown in the Nervión Estuary.
Technologically feasible	Equipment and technology obtained and successfully used, KCIs achieved; again, relying on BATNEEC; e.g. the marine habitats have been recreated/created/rehabilitated, and even re-planting and restocking are successful.
Societally tolerable/desirable	Societal wishes satisfied, aspirations likely to be satisfied, as the result of democracy and democratic processes; e.g., the marine area produces the goods and benefits required by society and is of the required aesthetic status.
Administratively achieved	KPIs of the administrative bodies have been achieved; e.g. the bodies deliver their required duties to satisfy the users and uses of the marine area.
Legally permissible	Avoidance of prosecution either by the individual or company, or, in the case of an EU state, by avoiding infraction proceedings at the ECJ, fulfilling all relevant legal instruments, especially by meeting the MSFD, WFD and other relevant directives for marine areas.
Politically expedient	Outcomes fit with nationally declared aims (e.g. fulfil national environment plans, EU strategies and policies, manifesto commitments).
Culturally inclusive	All types of groups and stakeholders satisfied, equity and justice achieved, including explicitly for gender, local communities and indigenous peoples, in decision-making; there is promotion of equal communities: everyone gets the support they need, to produce equality in management.
Morally correct/ethically defensible	No present conflicts or no future adverse legacy, ensuring that costs of management, remediation, etc., are not disproportionately placed on future generations; just communities are promoted: the systemic barriers are removed, by management, addressing the causes of inequity through justice.
Effectively communicable	All parties aware that management has been successful and sustainable, explicitly including participation, stakeholder interaction has been effective; e.g. ocean literacy has been shown to be increasing and effective; e.g. for effective marine management, there is the opportunity for increasing input from SDG implementation, from the UN Decade of the Ocean, or the UN World Ocean Assessments (Borja et al., 2022; McKinley et al., 2023).

the delivery of defined actions, especially to allow coordination between the various stakeholders and bodies involved in marine management. This will then achieve coherence and equivalence in management actions and outcomes, especially necessary in complex and transboundary marine areas (Elliott et al., 2023).

Outside of this management context, science will always see the challenges of changing baselines, trends in environmental states, and increasing collective pressures and, therefore, not necessarily have the knowledge to confirm that the environment has been ‘successfully managed’. Science shows uncertainty from one experiment, study or assessment to the next whereas management success has to be judged against policy objectives, outcomes and outputs. Thus, we clearly need SMART policy objectives, plans and programmes, and expected regulatory and non-regulatory outputs and outcomes. As such, our analysis and the Basque Country and MSFD case-studies here lead us to the following conclusions and recommendations.

- (i) Demonstrating successful marine management requires long-term, interdisciplinary monitoring networks, covering multiple ecosystem components, thus providing fit-for-purpose knowledge to take informed management decisions, including the ability to restore marine systems.
- (ii) However, monitoring is not a management measure *per se* but is needed to show *a priori* what management is required and *a posteriori* whether the management actions were successful.
- (iii) Managing the recovery of degraded marine systems may take decades, although ecosystem components recover at different rates and depend on each other for recovery, both in structure and function, i.e. the speed and scale of recovery is habitat and function dependent.
- (iv) Given point (iii), monitoring indications of the success of management may both require and take many years due to the lag-time between management actions, the inertia and variability in the system and the resulting anthropogenic change in ecological structure and function (i.e. separating anthropogenic change from inherent variability, the signal-to-noise ratio).
- (v) Management success can be measured as creating or restoring ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits with more cost-benefit assessments of the latter; however, the recovery of the societal goods and benefits from restored ecosystem services may not recoup all of the investment in restoration.
- (vi) Successful finance-based environmental and operational management may deliver economic benefits for an industry or developer but, in economically-challenging times, these may be allowed by regulators in preference to environmental sustainability.
- (vii) The success of management relies on having an effective and efficient delegated competent authority and comprehensive legislative instruments which are vertically-integrated from local to global levels and horizontally-integrated across marine sectors.
- (viii) Success in management should be measured against well- and clearly-defined outcomes, e.g. the achieving of a vision, aims and objectives, rather than merely outputs (the number of reports, samples taken, data produced).
- (ix) Resorting to legal proceedings against a company or individual as the result of an activity not complying with an issued law, licence, authorisation or permit can be regarded as a failure of management; this is the same with an EU country facing infraction proceedings for failing a Directive.
- (x) Satisfying the wishes of all stakeholders, including the public, will be the sign of successful management but recognise that it may not be possible to satisfy all stakeholders; note there may be a political decision to authorize an activity despite potential adverse environmental effects (i.e. under the so-called IROPI, *imperative reasons of overriding public interest*).

- (xi) Management success requires a holistic view of sustainability and governance (as policies, politics, administration and legislation) including interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches and views, quantifying the 10-tenets/PESTLE approaches.
- (xii) Success relies on the promotion of ocean literacy, i.e. the need to make citizens aware of the problems and the possibility of solutions, as well as allowing and helping environmental managers and society at large to take management-informed decisions.
- (xiii) Marine management should view the marine environment as an organisation whereby success requires a systems approach and the same methods of risk and opportunity assessment and management as any other organisation.
- (xiv) Successful and effective marine management requires the many national, regional and global marine initiatives to have an impact.
- (xv) Finally, management success encompasses a well-defined planning cycle with a vision achieved as the result of objectives *leading to* actions carried out *leading to* outputs produced *leading to* outcomes achieved.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michael Elliott: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ángel Borja:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Roland Cormier:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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No data were used for the research described in the article.

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